

AI-Powered Quiz Generation and Feedback System

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Abstract - Transforming the scenario of educational assessment, automatic quiz generation has made it possible to generate questions automatically and also personalized feedback. Existing systems suffer in content validation and adaptive feedback related to ill-structured questions or even irrelevant questions as these systems cannot be adaptive enough to learning. This research paper discusses an AI-based quiz generation algorithm technique employing a Django tutor system for providing high-quality assessments based on multi-tiered validation and intelligent mechanisms of feedback. The system takes uploaded PDFs as corpus, verifies their content value with keyword-based validation and AI-driven validation, and generates multiple-choice questions from that PDF. The tutors can then review, edit, and deploy quizzes for learners, who try out the same with a timer. AI-powered feedback is used to explain wrong answers to the learner so that learning is reinforced. The framework improves the reliability in assessment, helps create quizzes efficiently, and personalizes the learner's experience. This solution scales out for cloud deployment, while evaluation metrics of question relevance, validation accuracy, and engagement demonstrate improvement. It is possible for the educator to develop such lean assessments, thus enhancing learning outcomes in digital classrooms. The AI-driven feedback mechanism extends beyond automated answer validation and integrates contextual explanations related to wrong answers, as well as offers personalized instruction, thus aiding the learner to figure out the concept of the matter instead of simply memorizing an answer.

Keywords- *mcq generator, generative ai, AI-driven validation, large language models, context-aware NLP.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The assessment process has been disrupted by artificial intelligence-supported quiz generation, which allows automated question generation, validation, and feedback. Conventional quiz systems remain labor-intensive for teachers to come up with appropriate questions and assess student

performance. Yet with the use of AI Natural Language Processing (NLP) in the process, automation ensures that quizzes conform to learning objectives and feedback enhances students' contextual understanding. This seminar will present an AI-based quiz generation system based on Django that can analyze educational PDFs, validate their relevance to the content, generate MCQs, and provide AI feedback.

A. Challenges in Traditional Quiz Creation

The manual preparation of quizzes is highly time-consuming and is subject to human bias at different levels, resulting in inconsistency with regard to the degrees of difficulty and relevance of questions to the subject matter. Furthermore, closely validating whether or not questions represent key learning objectives requires a lot of attention from the educator. Existing automated quiz systems mainly use keyword matching, which is not context-sensitive; thus, the question becomes irrelevant or ambiguous instead.

B. Need for AI-Driven Quiz Generation and Feedback

Largely question restricted, the conventional systems of assessment do not at all provide an after- assessment feed back. Scored but with no detailed explanation on wrong answers, the learning potential of students ends there. This system has been improved so much, through AI based validation, context aware NLP and automated feedback generation, and it enhances question relevance, assessment efficiency, and paves way for student learning outcome.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Relevant research on automated generation and evaluation of multiple-choice quizzes explores the use of transformer models like BERT to generate questions from input sequences, context paragraphs, and response phrases through fine tuning. These models, including variations that integrate sequential data and context/answer tokens, have been shown to improve

question quality and reduce ambiguity in the generated content [1].

Further studies compare the quality of MCQs generated by AI models, such as ChatGPT, to those created by human experts, particularly in specialized fields like medical education. While human-generated questions often score higher on relevance, the overall quality of AI-generated MCQs demonstrates the potential of these models to perform on par with human efforts, showing no significant differences in key areas such as difficulty and clarity [2]. Additional work focuses on using transformer models, such as T5, in an end-to-end MCQ generation pipeline. This approach covers the entire process, from parsing and generating question-answer pairs to distractor creation, similarity scoring, and final question preparation, showcasing the capabilities of such models in automating comprehensive quiz generation [3].

Several other papers surveyed different techniques and approaches for automated MCQ generation from text data. Some utilized natural language processing methods like summarization, keyword extraction, distractor generation [4-7], and concept hierarchy extraction [8]. Other studies focused on neural question generation models with attention mechanisms [9] or leveraged large language models like GPT4 [10] and BERT [11] for specialized domains like programming education. Some studies proposed hybrid approaches combining rule-based and learning-based methods as shown in [11]. Evaluating the quality of generated MCQs through expert reviews, language model scoring, and metrics was also explored [12].

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

This system named AI-Based Quiz Generation and Feedback will be helpful in automating quiz creation with Natural Language Processing (NLP) post-evaluation feedback. The proposed system will consist of PDF-based question extraction, AI-based validation, multiple-choice questions (MCQs), and real-time feedback mechanisms revolving around the assessment processes. The quiz generation, however, is based on the AI Model. Furthermore, generating keywords and AI-based validation would lead to question generation and intelligent feedback mechanisms for better learning-satisfactory experience improvements.

A. User Interface of AI-Driven Quiz Generation System

The AI-Driven Quiz Generation System is small and effective, having been designed especially for tutors to generate quizzes from educational PDFs. As shown in the images, the system lets the tutors upload the document, set some parameters for the quiz, and result in AI-generated multiple choice questions (MCQs) almost effortlessly. Tutors start by uploading whatever combination of lecture notes, textbooks, or study materials found in a PDF. They proceed to enter their question number, specify a classroom, and indicate the test type (i.e.,

quiz or exam), thereafter powering up the AI question generation. The system ensures that the PDF uploaded meets specific criteria to ensure content relevance as well as educational integrity.

Once the required inputs are given, the tutor clicks on the button "Generate Questions," which in turn triggers the AI fused quiz generation scheme. The system then processes the document and essentially validates the content with the aid of some keyword-based filtering and a little bit of AI, before structuring the MCQs with four answer choices. The tutors are free to check the generated questions, edit them, approve them, and set them for the final quiz for the students. Some PDF Content Requirements are provided by the system to guide the tutors in ensuring the materials uploaded are good for quiz generation.

B. PDF Processing and Content Validation

The first step in the system is the PDF processing for meaningful educational content extraction. The system implements a two-tier verification process to ensure the extracted material is relevant and accurate. The initial verification procedure is Keyword-Based Verification. This implies scanning the document for predefined subject-specific keywords to be used as an initial filter to ascertain if the content is actually relevant towards the intended topic. If it does pass this level, then the document is subjected to the second-tier verification process, which is AI-Based Content Verification. This involves a transformer-based model that checks the semantic coherence and academic appropriateness of the document. Thus, this advanced validation step guarantees the incoming content for quiz generation is of high quality and contrastively relevant. Through the adoption of this dual-layered verification process, the system substantially decreases the chances of irrelevant or misleading questions being included, thus increasing the overall robustness and reliability of the resultant quizzes.

C. AI-Based Quiz Generation

The AI-driven quiz generation module, thereafter, formulates multiple-choice questions (MCQs) only after the content passes validation. Using the AI Model, the document is scrutinized for extracting major educational concepts while maintaining relevance and accuracy. It identifies essential topics and relationships while leveraging the Natural Language Processing mechanisms for the optimal creation of questions. Clear and coherent MCQs are then structured by the AI with consistent academic rigor. Each question would have one correct answer and three plausible distractors to enhance assessment quality. Thus, it would ensure that the generated quiz is indeed well-formed, logically framed, and aligned with learning objectives, providing a meaningful evaluation of the students' understanding.

D. Automated Feedback Mechanism

With the Automated Feedback Mechanism, an AI-powered feedback feature offered to students after completion of quizzes, learning is taken a step further as the system gives thorough explanation, performance analysis, and personalized improvement recommendations. When a student has selected an incorrect answer in a quiz question, the artificial intelligence generates contextual explanations that are based on how it would make a student understand why it was the wrong choice. Rather than merely showing the correct answer, the system gives logic according to concepts underlying the question, highlights misconceptions, and clears misalignments. This creates a deeper understanding of the question in regard to the misplaced choice rather than just stating where they went wrong. Ultimately, it improves learning outcomes for students by not just helping them recognize mistakes but also, understanding why those mistakes were made.

E. AI Model Utilization for Quiz Generation

The AI-based quiz-generating system uses analyses of educational PDFs to generate best-quality MCQs using Google's AI Model. The AI model has been tuned for natural language understanding (NLU) and the formulation of questions based on the content so that the generated assessments can be confidently expected to be contextualized and pedagogically solid.

The model processes textual input extracted from uploaded PDFs and applies transformer-based techniques to identify key educational concepts. The AI is fine-tuned to:

Extract essential information from structured academic text
Generate MCQ questions which are clear, cohesive, and grammatically correct

In order to ensure high standards, a two-level validation approach needs to be set up, which hinges on concept-keyword filtering for quality control and AI verification. Thus, guaranteeing that what finally goes into quiz generation is the highest quality and subject matter-focused. The feedback gives AI another chance of improvement and will continue to improve with the tutor's input in an iterative form for better educational outcome.

F. Workflow and AI Integration

Our AI-driven quiz generation system is deployed as a Django-based web application. The backend handles PDF processing, AI-based content validation, question generation, and quiz storage. AI Model for AI validation and question generation, ensuring high-quality assessments for students. The deployment follows a structured workflow:

Figure.1: Quiz Generation and Feedback Workflow

- The tutor uploads a PDF filled with study materials.
- The validation by keyword and AI decides upon the relevance of the content.
- The text from the extracted PDF document is transformed into multiple-choice questions by AI.
- The tutors review the quiz and finalize it.
- Students attempt the quiz and receive immediate feedback generated in real-time.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

It's got an AI-powered quiz generation component into our Django-based tutor system, and this paper evaluates how effective it is. Quite a lot was gained by our AI-led solutions, especially the provision of dual-stage validation to enhance content relevance and the generation of high-quality multiple-choice questions. Moreover, the automated feedback generation was analyzed with regard to its effect on student learning.

V. CONCLUSION

The automated quiz-generation engine that has been integrated into our tutor platform based on Django dramatically improves the productivity and accuracy of assessment evaluators. By employing a two-stage content validation process—keyword-based filtration in combination with AI validation using AI Model—we ensure that generated quizzes are highly relevant and of top quality. AI-generated multiple-choice questions with their automated feedback offer a more interactive and adaptive experience to students. It lowers the workload for tutors and promotes a data-driven and more exciting approach to education. Future enhancements may

expand AI features to make subjective questions or adaptable levels of difficulty possible for an even more personalized learning experience.

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